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Effect of nano fly ash hybridization on thermomechanical properties of sisal fiber reinforced polypropylene composite

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Introduction: Fabrication of synthetic fibers to be used for polymer composite manufacturing lead to the generation of immense waste and energy consumption. Natural fibers could be the perfect and techno-economic answer to these synthetic counterparts. Due to their environment friendly and moderately good mechanical properties, they create a huge opportunity to implement them in different engineering and commercial applications. However, poor interfacial adhesion between fresh natural fiber and polymer matrix leads to reduced mechanical, thermal and thermomechanical properties. Any physical or chemical compatibilization between interfaces of reinforcing fiber and base matrix enhances these properties significantly. Likewise, treatment of natural fiber, addition of a suitable coupling agent or hybridization with a filler may enhance aforementioned characteristics. For instance, FA hybridized sisal fiber reinforced PP composite prepared earlier by Maurya *et al.* showed improved mechanical, thermal and thermomechanical properties (1). Sodium hydroxide-3 aminopropyl tryethoxysilane (NaOH-APTES) treated sisal fiber, maleic anhydride grafted SEBS (MAH-SEBS) and silane treated FA as a filler were all used for the fabrication of above-mentioned hybrid composites.

Methods: The activation of FA particle with 2, 4 and 6 wt.% of C-tab has been achieved by using high energy planetary ball milling (Make: Retsch Germany) in ethylene acetate and 250 ml tungsten carbide medium at 250 rpm for 8 hours. SSL fibers were purchased from local vendor and 1 wt.% alkali followed by 2 wt.% of APTES treatment were given for effective silane coating. The hybrid composites were fabricated by feeding 85 wt.% PP, 10 wt.% SEBS, and 5 wt.% MAH-SEBS into the HAAKE™ Rheomix miniCTW twin screw mixer [Make:ThermoFisher SCIENTIFIC] in the temperature range of 185 to 190 °C. Fabrication of hybrid composites was achieved by adding FA and SSL fiber separately into the molten blend in the Rheomix. HAAKE 270 TM MiniCTW and HAAKE™ MiniJet II manufactured by ThermoFisher SCIENTIFIC was used to melt and mold in the desired shape of sample of the received chunks of composite from mixer. Appropriate temperature was used for melting (185 °C) and molding (2).

Results & Discussions: The lowest and highest storage modulus were recorded for 2 and 6 wt% C-tab treated FA hybrid composite. Likewise, the $\tan \delta$ value of the hybrid composite with 6 wt.% treatment of C-tab was found to be the least among all developed composites that confirmed better reinforcement of the matrix. Additionally, increment from 2 to 6 wt.% in the C-tab treatment concentration enhanced the E' although FA, SSL and BM amount were fixed for all the hybrid composite. This improvement was attributable to the good dispersion of FA in the matrix due to the addition of higher amount of surfactant C-tab. Likewise, there was very marginal improvement in the E' when treatment concentration was increased from 4 to 6 wt.% of the FA. This justifies the optimized treatment of 6 wt.% from C-tab. Decrease in the peak height of $\tan \delta$ of all the composites evidently shows reinforcing capability of SSL fiber.

Conclusions: All the 5 wt.% FA hybridized SSL reinforced PP composites shown improved E' value compared to pristine PP and composite reinforced with 30 wt.% of SSL alone. Use of MAH-SEBS and nano structured FA must have enhanced physical and chemical interactions between reinforcing SSL fiber and base matrix.

Keywords: Hybrid composite, Nano Fly-ash, Thermo-mechanical behavior,

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